

Live Shopping as a Digital Marketing Strategy: Its Impact on Purchase Interest and Customer Loyalty

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Abstract—This study aims to examine the influence of sales promotions, influencer credibility, and user experience on customer loyalty through buyer interest in the context of live shopping on two e-commerce platforms, namely Shopee Live and TikTok Shop. The research method employed is a quantitative explanatory approach with partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). Data was collected using an online survey involving 461 respondents from various regions in Indonesia. The analysis results indicate that sales promotions, influencer credibility, and user experience have a significant influence on buyer interest. Furthermore, buyer interest also significantly influences customer loyalty. All relationships between variables in the structural model were found to be significant based on bootstrapping tests. This study contributes to the development of digital marketing strategies using live commerce in Indonesia and reinforces the role of purchase interest as a mediating variable in building customer loyalty.

Keywords—Live shopping, digital marketing, sales promotion, influencer credibility, user experience, purchase intention, customer loyalty, PLS-SEM

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology and the internet has driven the rapid growth of the e-commerce sector,

especially in Indonesia. Online transaction activities using e-commerce are increasing from year to year. E-commerce is currently one of the fastest-expanding digital sectors in the Southeast Asia region, including Indonesia [1]. Easy access, fast transactions, affordable operating costs, and the integration of social media and e-commerce also encourage the buying interest of the Indonesian people [2].

One of the important innovations created in e-commerce today is live shopping. Live shopping is a combination of online shopping techniques that incorporate the latest broadcast technology, enabling two-way communication to occur directly. This concept provides convenience to customers, as they can observe products, ask questions and receive answers from sellers, and complete purchase transactions during the event session [3]. The popularity of live shopping has increased dramatically in Indonesia, particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic, which has limited people's physical activity. In this context, platforms such as Shopee Live and TikTok Shop serve as attractive interactive shopping solutions that cater to the needs of modern consumers [4].

Live shopping not only serves as a new channel for conveying product information, but also creates a more interactive and personalized shopping experience. This approach is proven to build consumer trust, encourage impulse purchases, and accelerate the sales conversion process [5]. These aspects are important in understanding how digital marketing

strategies work in the current era. Furthermore, gamification elements such as point and level systems, interactive games, and loyalty rewards presented during live sessions are proven to increase consumers' emotional engagement and influence their intention to buy [6]. Persuasive communication, built by presenters or influencers through speech style, gestures, or sentence choice, also has a significant impact on shaping consumer purchasing decisions [7].

Previous studies have evaluated the influence of promotion, interactivity, and influencer credibility on purchase intention, although most have been conducted partially [8]. However, not many studies have comprehensively evaluated the relationship between sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience on customer loyalty, especially in live shopping sessions in Indonesia [9]. In addition, most previous studies have focused more on short-term effects, such as purchase decision-making, without considering the formation of long-term relationships, including customer loyalty, which should also be built through trust and positive experiences during live sessions [10].

Based on this background, this study aims to evaluate the impact of sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience on customer loyalty in the context of live shopping. In addition, this study aims to simultaneously measure the impact of these three variables on customer loyalty across two leading platforms: Shopee Live and TikTok Shop.

About these objectives, the problem formulation in this study includes two main questions. First, how much influence do sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience have on customer loyalty in live shopping? Second, whether the three variables simultaneously have a significant influence on customer loyalty.

This study is limited to active e-commerce users in Indonesia, specifically those who have utilized the live shopping features on Shopee Live and TikTok Shop in recent months. The study focuses on three independent variables, namely sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience, and one dependent variable, namely customer loyalty.

This research is expected to provide both academic and practical benefits. Academically, this research contributes to the development of the literature on digital consumer behaviour and live commerce-based marketing strategies. The results of this study can serve as a reference for e-commerce industry players in developing effective strategies to increase customer loyalty by optimizing live shopping features.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on previous research, this study examines issues related to live shopping, digital marketing, customer loyalty, and consumer behaviour within the context of e-commerce, with a particular focus on Indonesia.

A research study conducted by Wongkitrungrueng and Assarut [1] shows that live streaming can increase a customer's trust in the seller by offering a variety of new shopping experiences within the e-commerce world that are more personalised and engaging. Another study conducted by Refiyahya and Azhar [3] also demonstrates that time pressure or limited time, as well as promotions with limited time, can increase consumer behaviour to make impulse purchases.

According to another study conducted by Mulyandani and Wulandani [4], the elements of ease of access and interactivity in TikTok Shop have a significant influence on increasing user buying interest. Putri and Masnita [5] also stated that digital social interaction and two-way communication can increase customer emotional engagement.

Another study conducted by Amelia et al. [10] found that brand trust built through direct or live interactions can increase customer loyalty. In another study, Sholikhah and Rokhmat [8] explained that the combination of influencer credibility and content marketing can influence the final purchase decision. The studies that have been revealed are the basis for developing a conceptual model in this study.

A. Literature Discussion and Research Gaps

Several studies have demonstrated that interactivity, sales promotion, and influencer credibility are crucial components in live shopping marketing strategies. However, the majority of previous studies only examine the variables separately or in a context outside Indonesia.

For example, Wongkitrungrueng and Assarut's study [1] focuses on consumer trust in a global context, but does not explore customer loyalty after purchase. The study conducted by Refiyahya and Azhar [3] emphasises the impact of promotions on impulse buying behaviour, but does not explore long-term relationships with customer loyalty.

Meanwhile, Sholikhah and Rokhmat [8] combine content marketing and influencer marketing, but their focus is limited to purchase decision-making, not customer retention. Only a few studies have investigated the relationship between user experience during live streaming and customer loyalty [5].

Therefore, this study fills the gap by combining sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience as the primary variables, and customer loyalty as the dependent variable, within a single empirical model in the Indonesian context.

B. Research Model

This research study model was developed based on a combination of previous research results and identified literature gaps. The three main independent variables studied, namely:

- Sales Promotions, such as flash sales, bundling, and direct gifts [3], [8].
- Influencer Credibility as expertise, honesty, attractiveness [8].
- User Experience as interactivity, immersion, navigation convenience [5].

All of these variables are considered to have an indirect influence on the dependent variable, specifically customer loyalty, through their impact on purchase intention [10]. This model will test whether the indirect path is statistically significant.

C. Research Hypothesis

Berdasarkan model tersebut dan literatur yang telah dikaji, maka hipotesis yang dirumuskan adalah sebagai berikut:

- Based on this model and the literature that has been reviewed, the hypotheses formulated are as follows:
- H1: Sales promotion in live shopping has a positive influence on purchase intention [3], [11].
- H2: Influencer credibility in live shopping has a positive influence on purchase intention [8], [12].
- H3: User experience in live shopping sessions positively influences purchase intention [5], [13].
- H4: Purchase intention has a positive effect on customer loyalty [1], [4], [10].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research employed an explanatory quantitative approach to investigate the causal relationship between variables, including sales promotion, influencer credibility and reliability, and user experience, and their impact on customer loyalty through purchase intention as a mediating variable. This approach is suitable for the research objectives that aim to explain the influence of variables through statistical analysis [1]. The data collection method chosen was a survey with a questionnaire developed based on indicators from previous research [3].

B. Population and Sample

The population of this study consists of active e-commerce users in Indonesia who have utilised live shopping features (such as Shopee Live or TikTok Shop) within the last six months. The sampling

technique used was purposive sampling, with the following criteria: (1) users aged 17 years or older; (2) have watched or purchased through live shopping. A total of 461 valid respondents were collected. This size has met the minimum requirements for analysis using Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), which is more than or equal to 10 times the most significant indicator in one construct [14].

C. Variables and Operational Definitions

This study examines five key variables: sales promotion, influencer credibility, user experience, purchase intention, and customer loyalty. Each variable is operationally defined, and its sources are indicated in Table 1.

Table I. Operational Definition of Variables

Variable	Indicator	Source
Sales Promotion	Flash sale, discount, direct gift	[9]
Influencer Credibility	Attractiveness, honesty, expertise	[8]
User Experience	Interactivity, convenience, information	[5]
Purchase Intention	Desire to try, actual purchase intention	[13]
Customer Loyalty	Loyalty, repeat purchase, recommendation	[10]

The measurement scale uses a 5-point Likert scale, from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (5).

D. Data Collection Technique

Data was collected using a questionnaire (Google Form) distributed through social media, group chats, and friendship networks. The instrument was pilot-tested on 30 respondents to assess the clarity of the wording and content validity. Once refined, the questionnaire was used in the official deployment for the main data collection. The questionnaire consisted of close-ended items measured using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (5).

E. Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis was conducted in two stages:

1. Measurement Model Testing (Outer Model): Instrument validity and reliability were tested using outer loading values (≥ 0.7), average variance extracted ($AVE \geq 0.5$), and Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.7) [15].
2. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model): Evaluation indicators include path coefficient, R^2 value, and significance value (p-value) based on bootstrapping with 5,000 resampling [14].

IV. Results and Discussion

A. Description of Respondents

This study involved 461 respondents from several regions in Indonesia without geographical restrictions. Based on gender, 209 respondents (45.3%) were male, and 252 respondents (54.7%) were female. This finding suggests that the distribution of respondents between the male and female genders is relatively balanced, although there is a slight predominance of female respondents. In terms of age group, the majority of respondents are in the age range of 18-24 years old as many as 381 people (82.6%), while a total of 28 respondents (6.1%) are in the age group of 25-34 years old, while other respondents are outside the age range or do not provide age-related information.

Regarding the habit of using the live shopping feature, 139 respondents (30.2%) reported using it occasionally, while 101 respondents (21.9%) stated that they rarely use it. There were no respondents who stated that they frequently use the live shopping feature. These results indicate that the majority of respondents are young digital users with moderate to low exposure to live shopping features. Thus, the respondents' characteristics are relevant enough to test the impact of live shopping on purchase intention and customer loyalty in this digital era.

B. validity and reliability test

Table II. Outer loadings

Indicator <-Construct	Outer loadings
KI1 <- KI (Influencer Credibility)	0,738
KI2 <- KI (Influencer Credibility)	0,763
KI3 <- KI (Influencer Credibility)	0,725
KI4 <- KI (Influencer Credibility)	0,790
KI5 <- KI (Influencer Credibility)	0,722

LP1 <- LP (Customer Loyalty)	0,792
LP2 <- LP (Customer Loyalty)	0,864
LP3 <- LP (Customer Loyalty)	0,880
LP4 <- LP (Customer Loyalty)	0,836
LP5 <- LP (Customer Loyalty)	0,802
MP1 <- MP (Purchase Intention)	0,865
MP2 <- MP (Purchase Intention)	0,878
MP3 <- MP (Purchase Intention)	0,874
MP4 <- MP (Purchase Intention)	0,895
MP5 <- MP (Purchase Intention)	0,819
PA1 <- PA (User Experience)	0,721
PA2 <- PA (User Experience)	0,796
PA3 <- PA (User Experience)	0,854
PA4 <- PA (User Experience)	0,861
PA5 <- PA (User Experience)	0,800
PP1 <- PP (Sales Promotion)	0,829
PP2 <- PP (Sales Promotion)	0,845
PP3 <- PP (Sales Promotion)	0,786
PP4 <- PP (Sales Promotion)	0,855
PP5 <- PP (Sales Promotion)	0,770

1) Outer Loading: Outer loading analysis is used to assess the convergent validity of each indicator against the measured construct. Based on the results of the processed data, all indicators in the research model have outer loading values above the recommended minimum threshold of 0.7, indicating that each indicator makes a significant contribution to measuring its latent construct. For example, the MP5 indicator has the highest value of 0.895 for the Purchase Intention construct. Then followed by the MP4 (0.885) and LP (0.864) indicators for Customer Loyalty. All indicators are within the acceptable value range, so no indicators need to be eliminated. This finding supports the construct validity of the model and indicates that all indicators used have met the statistical criteria for further testing.

2) Cronbach's Alpha: The reliability analysis, using Cronbach's Alpha, indicates that all constructs in this study exhibit good internal consistency. The Cronbach's Alpha value for each construct is as follows: Influencer Credibility (0.803), Customer Loyalty (0.891), Purchase Intention (0.917), User Experience (0.867), and Sales Promotion (0.875). All of these values exceed the minimum threshold of 0.70, which is commonly used as an indicator of acceptable reliability. This finding indicates that the indicator items for each construct demonstrate a high level of consistency in measuring the variable in question, ensuring that the data obtained in this study are reliable.

3) Average variance extracted: Convergent validity analysis in this study utilises the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, which indicates the extent to which the latent constructs can explain the variance in the indicators. An adequate Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is above 0.50, indicating that the construct can explain more than 50% of the variance in the indicators that comprise it. Based on the calculation results, all constructs in this study meet these criteria, with the following details: Influencer Credibility (0.559), Customer Loyalty (0.698), Purchase Intention (0.751), User Experience (0.653), and Sales Promotion (0.668). Thus, all constructs in this model have met the criteria for convergent validity, indicating that each construct can effectively represent its constituent indicators.

4) Composite Reliability: Composite reliability analysis is conducted to measure the internal consistency of indicators in measuring latent constructs. The recommended composite reliability value is above 0.70. Based on the output results, all constructs in this study have met these criteria, with the following details: Influencer Credibility (0.864), Customer Loyalty (0.920), Purchase Intention (0.938), User Experience (0.904), and Sales Promotion (0.910). All composite reliability values are pretty far above the recommended minimum limit, indicating that each construct in the model has excellent reliability. This finding further supports the reliability and suitability of the measurement instruments used in this study for further analysis.

5) Discriminant Validity (HTMT): Discriminant validity in this study was evaluated using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) approach, with a threshold of 0.90 indicating adequate discriminant validity. Based on the results of the HTMT matrix and list analysis, all values between constructs are below the specified threshold, thus indicating the fulfilment of discriminant validity. For example, the HTMT value between Customer Loyalty and Influencer Credibility is 0.845, between Purchase Intention and User Experience is 0.830, and between Sales

Promotion and User Experience is 0.849. These values indicate that each construct in the model exhibits a distinct level of difference from the other constructs. Thus, it can be concluded that the model has met the discriminant validity criteria required in the PLS-SEM approach.

C. R-square

Figure 1. Structural Model (PLS Algorithm Result)

Based on the SmartPLS output displayed in Figure 1, the R-squared (R^2) value for the Purchase Intention (MP) construct is 0.646, while for the Customer Loyalty (LP) construct, it is 0.667. This R^2 value indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that the independent variables in the research model can explain. In this case, the R^2 value of 0.646 in the Purchase Intention (MP) construct indicates that the combined effects of Sales Promotion, Influencer Credibility, and User Experience can explain 64.6% of the variability in Purchase Intention. Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.667 in LP indicates that the Purchase Intention variable can explain 66.7% of the variability of Customer Loyalty. Both of these R^2 values fall into the strong category, according to Chin (1998), indicating that the structural model used has good predictive power for endogenous constructs.

D. Hypothesis Test (Bootstrapping)

Figure 2. Structural Model (PLS Algorithm Result)

As shown in Figure 2, hypothesis testing was conducted using a bootstrapping approach with 5,000 resamples, aiming to assess the significance of the

relationships between constructs in the structural model. The results of this analysis indicate that all the relationship paths between variables have T-statistic values exceeding 1.95 and P-values of 0.000, which are well below the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that all relationships in the model are statistically significant. The path coefficient value indicates that purchase intention (MP) has a powerful influence on customer loyalty (LP), with a value of 0.817, which is supported by the highest T-statistic value of 39.643. This suggests that the greater a customer's interest in making purchases through live shopping, the higher their loyalty to the product or brand will be.

In addition, the sales promotion variable (PP) has a relatively strong direct influence on purchase intention (MP), with a coefficient of 0.380, as well as the values of influencer credibility (KI) at 0.291 and user experience (PA) at 0.227. All three also have an indirect influence on customer loyalty through buyer interest. All coefficient values are within the 95% confidence interval range that does not include zero, so that both in ordinary and bias-corrected interval calculations, which strengthens the validity of the influence. Thus, this research model has been empirically proven to have strong predictive power, and all hypotheses proposed in this study are accepted based on valid and statistically significant test results.

E. Discussion

1) Interpretation of results: The interpretation of the results in this study indicates that the model built has good measurement quality. All indicators have an outer loading value above 0.7, which indicates that each indicator represents its respective construct. The values of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability for all constructs are also above 0.7, indicating high internal consistency between items within each variable. Furthermore, the AVE value of all constructs is above 0.5, which explains that more than 50% of the indicator variance can be explained by the latent construct, thus meeting the criteria for convergent validity. The R-square values for the purchase interest construct, namely 0.646, and customer loyalty, namely 0.667, fall into the strong category, indicating that the model can explain a substantial proportion of the variability in the two constructs. Finally, the results of hypothesis testing through bootstrapping yielded p-values < 0.05 for all paths, indicating that all relationships between variables in the model are statistically significant. These findings overall support the hypotheses proposed in the study and strengthen the validity of the conceptual model used.

2) Comparison with Previous Research: The results of this study indicate that Sales Promotion, Influencer Credibility, and User experience have a

significant influence on purchase intention. Furthermore, Purchase Interest is proven to have a positive impact on customer loyalty. These findings are also in line with Refiyahya and Azhar's research [3], which found that urgency-based promotions cause impulsive consumers to make purchases. This finding is also in line with Sholikhah and Rokhmat's research [8], which shows that the credibility of an influencer can strengthen consumer purchasing decisions. In addition, these results also support the study conducted by Putri and Masnita [5], which emphasises that interactivity and two-way communication play a crucial role in shaping a more substantial and more memorable user experience. However, no significantly conflicting results were found; instead, this study expands the literature by integrating the three variables into a single model that leads to customer loyalty in the context of live shopping in Indonesia.

3) Implications of Results for Theory or Topic: The findings of this study support consumer behavior theory which states that purchasing decisions can be influenced by perceived value, experience, as well as user trust and influencer credibility can be interpreted as a form of perceived value and source credibility that increases purchase intentions, as outlined in the theory of reasoned action. In addition, the results of this study can also reinforce the principles in digital marketing that emphasise the importance of engagement and personalisation in building customer loyalty. Therefore, this research supports the proposed hypothesis and is relevant to the theoretical framework employed.

4) Contribution to the Industry and State of the Art: This research makes a significant contribution to the industry, particularly in the development of digital marketing strategies utilising live shopping. The results of this research emphasise that to increase customer loyalty, industry players need to focus on building influencer credibility and creating a fun, interactive experience during live sessions, rather than just focusing on prices and promotions. In terms of state of the art, this research differs from previous studies in that it integrates three main variables, namely sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience, into one model through purchase intention in Indonesia, which is still rarely discussed in international literature. This combination makes this research practically and scientifically relevant.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to evaluate the effect of sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience on customer loyalty, with purchase intention as a mediating variable. The results showed that sales promotion, influencer credibility, and user experience

have a positive influence on purchase intention. Furthermore, in this study, purchase intention has a positive effect on purchase intention. Furthermore, purchase intention has a significant impact on customer loyalty. Thus, this study has demonstrated that a live shopping strategy incorporating the aforementioned points can enhance customer loyalty by influencing purchase intention.

However, there are also several limitations in this study, including, (1) the sample is limited to shopee live and tiktok shop users in Indonesia which may not be generalizable to the global market or other e-commerce platforms, (2) this study only focuses on specific variables in live shopping and does not consider other external factors that can affect customer loyalty.

For future research, it is recommended to examine other factors that can affect customer loyalty, such as price, product quality, or psychological elements that influence consumer decision-making. Further research can also analyze comparisons between various live shopping platforms to examine how differences between platforms impact purchase intention and customer loyalty.

VI. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Throughout this research, all team members played crucial roles and made substantial contributions. Jonathan Hansen (2702226363) acted as the Group Leader, responsible for coordinating the entire project. Jonathan created a Google Form for the survey, distributed the questionnaire, and analysed the data using the SmartPLS 4 application. Additionally, Jonathan read and studied the results from SmartPLS, compiled Chapter 4, sections “Hypothesis Test” and “Discussion,” and Chapter 5, “Conclusion.” He also helped insert tables and images, translated the paper results from Indonesian to English, edited the grammar using Grammarly, and finalized the document.

Kelvin Khonggo (2702248692) helped create the Google Form, distribute the survey, and analyse the data using SmartPLS 4. He also read and reviewed the analysis results and wrote Chapter 4, sections “Description of Respondents,” “Validity and Reliability Test,” and “R-Square.” Additionally, Kelvin worked on Chapter 5 and created a PowerPoint presentation covering pages 12–19.

Cikal Raiza Faisal (2702378413) played a role in preparing Chapter 2, “Literature Review,” helped compile and tidy up the bibliography, and collected respondents for the survey. He was also involved in creating a PowerPoint presentation for the “Research Method” section, covering slides 1 to 4.

Rajwa Habibi (2702382165) wrote Chapter 1, “Introduction,” and part of Chapter 2, “Literature Review,” specifically the sections on “Identification and List of Literature Sources,” “Literature Discussion and Research Gaps,” “Research Model,” and “Research Hypothesis.” She also contributed to the PowerPoint presentation from slides 5 to 11.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Wongkitrungrueng and N. Assarut, “The role of live streaming in building consumer trust and engagement with social commerce sellers,” *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 117, pp. 510–519, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.08.032>.
- [2] E. Hartawan, D. Liu, M. R. Handoko, G. Evan, and H. Widjojo, “Pengaruh iklan di media sosial Instagram terhadap minat beli masyarakat pada e-commerce,” *JMBI UNSRAT (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis Dan Inovasi Universitas Sam Ratulangi)*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 217–228, 2021, doi: 10.35794/jmbi.v8i1.33853.
- [3] A. H. Refiyahya and A. Azhar, “Dari Live Streaming hingga Checkout: Memahami Impulse Buying di Shopee,” *Jurnal Penelitian Ilmiah Multidisiplin*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 210–216, 2025. <https://sejurnal.com/pub/index.php/jpim/article/view/6325>.
- [4] N. Mulyandani and O. A. D. Wulandani, “Pengaruh Siaran Langsung dan Kemudahan Terhadap Minat Beli Mahasiswa UCIC Pada Platform TikTok Shop”, *JAMEK*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 232-240, Sep. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.47065/jamek.v4i3.1475>.
- [5] A. M. Putri and Y. Masnita, “Pengaruh Interaktivitas dan Social Presence platform terhadap Minat Beli pada Live Stream Online Shopping di E-Commerce,” *Innovative*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 8377–8392, 2024. <https://j-innovative.org/index.php/Innovative/article/view/7434>.
- [6] M. Putri and M. Mayasari, “Pengaruh gamifikasi terhadap niat membeli kembali pada e-commerce Shopee,” *Jurnal Akuntansi, Ekonomi dan Manajemen Bisnis*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 90–99, Dec. 2022. DOI:10.30871/jaemb.v10i2.4686.
- [7] V. V. Yanthi and S. Azeharie, “Pengaruh komunikasi persuasif pada live shopping TikTok,” *Prologia*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 230–239, Mar. 2024.
- [8] D. A. Sholikhah and R. Rokhmat, “Pengaruh Content Marketing, Viral Marketing, dan Influencer Marketing terhadap Purchase Decision pada Pengguna Social Commerce TikTok Shop di Yogyakarta,” *Co-Value J. Ekon., Koperasi & Kewirausahaan*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2024, doi: 10.59188/covalue.v15i3.4620.
- [9] N. Yurindera, “Minat Beli pada Live Shopping TikTok berdasarkan Sales Promotion dan Influencer Credibility,” *J. Esensi Infokom*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2023.
- [10] R. Amelia, A. Kautsar, and D. T. W. Wardoyo, “Digital marketing strategy for customer loyalty with the role of brand positioning and trust mediation,” *2024 Int. Conf. on Cyber and IT Service Management (CITSM)*, Batam, Indonesia, pp. 1–6, 2024, doi: 10.1109/CITSM64103.2024.10775701.
- [11] L. N. Ramadhani and D. A. Nugroho, “Pengaruh Live Streaming, Flash Sale, dan Hedonic Shopping Motivation terhadap Impulsive Buying,” *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran dan Perilaku Konsumen*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 207–215, 2024, doi: 10.21776/jmppk.2024.03.1.21.
- [12] E. N. Siregar, Pristiyono, and M. A. Al Ihsan, “Analysis of Using Tiktok as Live Marketing in Attracting Consumers’ Interest in Buying,” *Quantitative Economics and Management Studies (QEMS)*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 453-463, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454RI.qems1633>.

- [13] S. Maharani and I. M. B. Dirgantara, “Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Immersion Saat Live Streaming Syaria Shopping Serta Pengaruhnya Kepada Minat Pembelian (Studi Pada Social Commerce Tik Tok Indonesia)”, *JIEI*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 2942–2955, Jul. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.29040/jiei.v9i2.9854>.
- [14] F. F. Aulianur and M. S. Purwanegara, “The analysis of factors driving consumer engagement and purchase intention in e-commerce live streaming,” Undergraduate Thesis, School of Business and Management ITB, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.59613/mjbms.v3i1.141>
- [15] J. F. Hair Jr., G. T. M. Hult, C. M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt, *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, 2014.